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Research Article

**A COMPARISON BETWEEN CONVENTIONAL & LAPAROSCOPIC
CHOLECYSTECTOMY WITH RELATED COMPLICATIONS, PAIN,
ANALGESIC & ANTIBIOTIC REQUIREMENT****¹Dr. Habib Ullah Sajid, ²Dr. Ulfat Hassan, ¹Dr. Asad Masood Khokhar**¹Rashid Latif Medical College Lahore²Sargodha Medical College, Sargodha**Abstract:**

Background and Objectives: There is a rapid establishment of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) popularity over conventional open cholecystectomy (OC) with a debate on the topic of effectiveness and safety aspects. Therefore, the aim of our research is to draw a comparison of both approaches with respect to procedural durations, postoperative pain, postoperative complications, antibiotic requirement, analgesic requirement, normal diet resumption and duration of hospitalization.

Material and Methods: We completed this comparative research study in the timeframe of April to December 2017 at Services Hospital, Lahore (Medicine Department). Our research sample population consisted of fifty acalculous cholecystitis/ acute calculous patients which were diagnosed through ultrasonography. Patients experienced at least one upper abdominal pain attack; such patients of both male and female gender became a part of the research sample for onward investigations.

Results: The most involved age racket was of the fifth decade especially among the female population with the most repeated pain incidence of abdomen RUQ. Every patient had a presentation of gallbladder stones as observed through ultrasonography. In terms of procedural duration, the LC took more time than OC with respective time duration of 120 minutes and 90 minutes. There were eight percent cases of conversion from LC to OC. LC operated cases were more frequent in postoperative morbidity. LC group required less amount of analgesic and antibiotic than OC group. Diet resumption was also earlier among the patient of LC than OC (two days earlier); whereas, hospitalization was also less in the patients treated with LC than OC (four days difference).

Conclusion: Outcomes portray about the acalculous cholecystitis/ acute calculous incidence dominance in the female population. The most frequent presentation was also available in the age bracket of the fifth decade with abdomen pain symptoms. Most common diagnostic tool was ultrasonography. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy takes a fewer analgesic & antibiotic, hospitalization, pain leading to disability, better cosmesis and wound infection than open cholecystectomy. Whereas, the operative time period was more in laparoscopic cholecystectomy than open cholecystectomy which can possibly be reduced through better and increased learning session and experience.

Keywords: Acalculous Cholecystitis, Acute Calculous, Ultrasonography, Abdominal, Analgesic, Antibiotic, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy (LC) and Open Cholecystectomy (OC).

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INTRODUCTION:

A revolution has been made in the field of gastrointestinal surgical procedures with the advent and introduction of laparoscopic methods [1]. Calculous cholecystitis/ Acute acalculous, known as repeated digestive disorders were managed through open (conventional) cholecystectomy [2]. The surgical community received a new and better alternative to the conventional approach in the form of laparoscopic interventional strategies for better postoperative outcomes [3].

LC is no doubt safer and effective with the easy approach as the magnification is better than ever. Its clear merits include reduced hospitalization, decreased morbidity, rapid recovery to continue normal routine and cosmetic merits as well [4]. Few surgeons also report about the severe bile duct injury complications in LC procedures [5]. Specialized training and costly laparoscopic equipment are mandatory for better and effective outcomes and with reduced risk involvement [6].

There is a rapid establishment of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) popularity over conventional open cholecystectomy (OC) with a debate on the topic of effectiveness and safety aspects. Therefore, the aim of our research is to draw a comparison of both approaches with respect to procedural durations, postoperative pain, postoperative complications, antibiotic requirement, analgesic requirement, normal diet resumption and duration of hospitalization.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We completed this comparative research study in the timeframe of April to December 2017 at Services Hospital, Lahore (Medicine Department). Our research sample population consisted of fifty acalculous cholecystitis/ acute calculous patients which were diagnosed through ultrasonography. Patients experienced at least one upper abdominal pain attack; such patients of both male and female gender became a part of the research sample for onward investigations. We did not include any

patient presenting SBD Stones, prior abdominal surgery history, above seventy years aged patients and coagulopathy patients who received an anticoagulant management in the research sample. Hospital's ethical review committee gave written permission to start with the research protocols with an informed consent of the research participants.

Group – I and II included respectively twenty-five patients each and these groups were respective LC and OC groups in order to compare the focused outcomes. No dietary intake was given except a prophylactic antibiotic dose prior to surgical intervention. We also made sure that every patient goes to the operation theatre with an empty bladder and also passed a nasogastric tube on a need basis. Surgeries were carried out under general anaesthesia by an expert team of surgeons which include both residents and consultants. Statistical analysis was carried out through Z-Test and Chi-Square Test.

RESULTS:

The most involved age racket was of the fifth decade especially among the female population with the most repeated pain incidence of abdomen RUQ. Every patient had a presentation of gallbladder stones as observed through ultrasonography. In terms of procedural duration, the LC took more time than OC with respective time duration of 120 minutes and 90 minutes. There were eight percent cases of conversion from LC to OC. LC operated cases were more frequent in postoperative morbidity. LC group required less amount of analgesic and antibiotic than OC group. Diet resumption was also earlier among the patient of LC than OC (two days earlier); whereas, hospitalization was also less in the patients treated with LC than OC (four days difference). Detailed outcomes about the surgical procedure duration, surgical procedure complications, postoperative complications, antibiotic intake, postoperative intake, normal diet resumption, hospitalization and clinical outcomes are given in the tabular and graphical presentation (Table – I to VIII)

Table – I: Surgical Procedure Duration in Minutes

Time (Minutes)	Open Cholecystectomy	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy
60 – 90	9	0
90 – 120	11	8
120 – 150	5	14
> 150	0	3

Table – II: Surgical Procedure Associated Complications

Complications	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy		Open Cholecystectomy	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Bleeding	1	4	2	8
Bile duct injury	0	0	0	0
Bowel injury	0	0	0	0
Others	0	0	0	0
Total	1	4.00	2	8.00

Table – III: Preoperative Complications

Complications	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy		Open Cholecystectomy	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Bleeding	0	0	0	0
Bile leak through drain	0	0	3	12
Wound infection	2	8	0	0
Jaundice	0	0	0	0
Post cholecystectomy syndrome	0	0	2	8
Pulmonary complications	0	0	0	0
Total	2	8.00	5	20.00

Table – IV: Antibiotic Intake Duration

Days	Open Cholecystectomy	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy
Under 4	0	19
4 – 6	8	4
Above 6	17	2

Table – V: Day Wise Postoperative Pain

Postoperative Pain	Open Cholecystectomy	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy
First Day	25	25
Second Day	25	5
Third Day	20	3
Fourth Day	15	0
Fifth Day	10	0
Sixth Day	5	0

Table – VI: Normal Diet Consumption

Days	Open Cholecystectomy	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy
Under 3	0	19
3 – 4	10	4
Above 4	15	2

Table – VII: Hospitalization

Days	Open Cholecystectomy	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy
Under 3	0	20
3 – 5	7	3
Above 5	18	2

Table – VIII: Detailed Clinical Outcomes

Variables	Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy		Open Cholecystectomy	
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD
Age (years)	42.76	12.09	39.12	13.79
Duration of surgery (min)	120	10.8	90	13.84
Analgesic requirement (days)	3.12	0.33	6.08	0.4
Antibiotic requirement (days)	4.28	0.46	7.4	1.58
Resumption of normal diet (days)	3.16	0.85	5.24	1.23
Postoperative hospital stay (days)	3.04	1.34	7.76	1.23

DISCUSSION:

Females had a dominance over males in both LC and OC groups. The outcomes about the longer operating duration were same as reported by Shazra, Porte and Trondsen as increased time has an association with difficult adhesions, intraoperative gas leakage, port side gallbladder delivery and slipping off the clips [3 – 8]. Operative time decreases with the learning curve and expertise in the procedure as familiarization with a new instrument and building confidence with speed, accuracy and consistency take time [8]. Minor complications were there such as leakage of the bile, loss of blood, postcholecystectomy syndrome and wound infection with various proportions in both groups of LC and OC. These complications were treated as a matter of routine.

OC group received wound infection in two groups;

whereas, LC group had no such case. The infection was treated through regular dressing in the timeframe of ten days. Harris and few other authors also reported the same outcomes of complications and reported leakage of bile, bleeding and wound infections as associated complications with varying proportions in both groups [9 – 11]. We reported eight percent cases of conversion from LC to OC; whereas, other research studies also reported a higher conversion rate from 0% to 45% [12 – 14]. An antibiotic and analgesic use was less in LC group than OC group which may have an association with less wound infection and incision size.

With the application of minimally invasive methods in the elective surgical procedures reduce the response of the inflammatory stress, decreased hypoxia and better pulmonary function [15 – 16]. VAS is better in LC group with significant P-Value

of (< 0.005). More onset of pain was among OC operated patients which ultimately required more intake of analgesics especially in the incidence of wound infection development. These signs may have an association with the reduced size of the incision used in LC groups; same reports are available in the outcomes of other studies [17 – 20].

LC groups resumed to a normal diet within two days; whereas, in the OC group it was three days. Seven days and five days was the maximum diet resumption time among OC and LC groups respectively. Among various benefits of LC over OC, rapid recovery and decreased hospital stay were more prominent [15]. In our research, mean hospitalization in LC and OC group was respectively three days and seven days with significant P-Value as (< 0.005).

Increased hospital stay in OC group was because of wound infections and increased pain which required increased use of antibiotics; same reports are found in the research outcomes of Lujan, Trondsen and Porte [7, 11, 13]. Few of the other research studies also confirmed these outcomes [21 – 22]. OC group received large size wounds in the shape of the big single scar. Less visible scar was reported in LC groups as the size of the incision was less than 1.5 centimetres. Therefore, LC is better than OC in terms of better cosmetic outcomes.

CONCLUSION:

Outcomes portray about the acalculous cholecystitis/ acute calculous incidence dominance in the female population. The most frequent presentation was also available in the age bracket of the fifth decade with abdomen pain symptoms. Most common diagnostic tool was ultrasonography. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy takes a fewer analgesic & antibiotic, hospitalization, pain leading to disability, better cosmesis and wound infection than open cholecystectomy. Whereas, the operative time period was more in laparoscopic cholecystectomy than open cholecystectomy which can possibly be reduced through better and increased learning session and experience.

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